

An e-learning collaborative filtering approach to suggest problems to solve in programming online judges

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ABSTRACT

The paper proposes a recommender system approach to cover online judge's domains. Online judges are e-learning tools that support the automatic evaluation of programming tasks done by individual users, and for this reason they are usually used for training students in programming contest and for supporting basic programming teachings. The proposal pretends to suggest problems assuming that a user must try to solve those problems already successfully solved by similar users. With this goal, we adopt the traditional collaborative filtering method with a new similarity measure adapted to the current domain, and we propose several transformations in the user-problem matrix to incorporate specific online judge's information. We evaluate the effect of the matrix configurations using Precision and Recall metrics, getting better results comparing with our method without transformations and with a representative state-of-art approach. Finally, we outline possible extensions to the current work.

Keywords: programming online judge, problem, users' fails, collaborative filtering, recommendation systems

INTRODUCTION

Programming online judges are applications that automate the process of compiling and testing the solutions to problems that the same tool contains. Each year the presence in the Web of these kinds of applications increases. Worth of note are the ACM-ICPC¹ Live Archive (<https://icpcarchive.ecs.baylor.edu/>), the Universidad de Valladolid Online Judge (UVa, <http://uva.onlinejudge.org/>), the Peking University Online Judge (<http://poj.org/>), the Sphere Online Judge (<http://www.spoj.com/>), the Ural State University Online Judge (<http://acm.timus.ru/>) and the Harbin Institute of Technology Online Judge (<http://acm.hit.edu.cn/hoj/>), which had hosted the training of some of the best teams in the ACM-ICPC programming contests around the world. In the Caribbean area, we also have the Caribbean Online Judge (<http://coj.uci.cu/>), used to support our ACM-ICPC teams.

¹ ACM International Collegiate Programming Contest

There is a worldwide tendency to extend the use of these applications toward the support of basic programming abilities, a super set of programming contests skills. Chief example of this is the EduJudge project (<http://eduvalab.uva.es/en/projects/edujudge-project>), whose only purpose is the integration of the UVa in an effective educational environment. Also in the University of Informatics Sciences (UCI), in Cuba, there had been some successful experiences focused on the integration of online judges into undergraduate courses programs.

As web applications, online judges are subject to the information overload associated to the World Wide Web in the last few years. The data maintained by the aforementioned applications include a great number of problems and registered users, and lots of code in the submitted solutions, both correct and erroneous. In the UCI intranet currently reside two online judges, containing 850+ problems, 1800+ users, and tens of thousands of solutions submitted, and growing. This amount of data causes that users usually are not able to select the appropriate problem to solve according to their profile.

A classical solution to this information overload is the development of recommender systems (Resnick & Varian, 1997) focused on specific domains. In this paper, we propose the application of traditional recommendation techniques to the new online judge domain, to obtain an online judge recommender system. Firstly, we make a brief overview of online judges, specifying their main functionalities and purposes. After this, we justify the novelty of the online judge recommender scenario over other current state-of-art e-learning recommenders. Then, we develop a new approach to recommend problems to solve in this scenario using their specific data, and we design an experiment to measure its accuracy against baseline methods. Finally, we show our conclusions and the future works.

OVERVIEW OF THE ONLINE JUDGES

Online judges usually host a list of problems to solve. When the user enters to the application, it has to choose an exercise to solve. Then, it must write a program as a solution to the selected problem, and after that, the system provides a screen to submit the solution. Once the user has submitted it, the system automatically compiles and runs it against a previously defined input dataset for the specific problem. If the obtained program output coincides with an also predefined output, the problem is considered as solved, or *accepted*, in the judge language. Otherwise, the problem is considered as not solved. When a user does not solve a problem, this failure can also be grouped in categories. The most important categories are (Skiena & Revilla, 2003):

- *Wrong Answer*: The program returns an incorrect answer to one or more of the judge's secret test case.
- *Compile Error*: The compiler could not figure out how to compile the code submitted.
- *Runtime Error*: The program fails during execution due to a segmentation fault, floating point exception, or similar problem.

- *Presentation Error*: The program outputs are correct, but are not presented in the specified format.
- *Time Limit Exceeded*: The program took more than established time to process all the inputs.

The automatic judge immediately informs to the user and stores the result of the submission. Finally, it ranks the users considering the particular amount of accepted problems.

In the last years, in addition to the presence of these applications in the web, also several researches in e-learning have been focused on automatic evaluation tools for programming tasks. Kurnia and Cheang formally present online judges in (Kurnia, Lim, & Cheang, 2001) (Cheang, Kurnia, Lim, & Wee, 2003), as tools to automatically evaluate source code solutions made by students, solving programming problems previously proposed. They also analyze its effect in the automated grading of programming assignments in an academic institution. Kosowski, Malafiejski and Noisni (2007) formally described the SPOJ online judge and contest system, used for e-learning of programming, and successfully applied in the tuition of students at the Gdańsk University of Technology. Finally, De la Fuente, Pardo and Delgado-Kloos (2013) present a system to support the automation of time consuming tasks in introductory programming courses, such as the delivery of activities or the submission grading. It automatically evaluates the student submissions and gradually unlocks the following activities depending on the received results.

To our best knowledge, there are no works in this scenario focused on suggest programming tasks to students, based on its previous behavior and its peers' behavior. Although traditional online judges like UVa have presented "next-to-solve" services that propose problems to solve based on the number of accepted solutions, there are no studies beyond that.

Disregarding a possible pedagogical use for the judges, the experience shows that the main users target in these applications is to solve the biggest amount of problems. However, in the bottom part of the ranking we can see that there is an important group of users with a very small number of problems solved, and a high number of failures. Professors and experienced users have considered that it occurs because many people are not able to select the right problem to solve, according to their current preference and interests, and considering the problems solved before. This is the main motivation to build a recommender system to support these applications.

RECOMMENDER SYSTEMS

Recommender systems are designed to present or suggest different subjects or items to specific users, based on the prediction of their preferences.

The most accepted definition for the recommendation problem is established in (Adomavicius & Tuzhilin, 2005) and is formulated as follows. Let C be the set of all users and let S be the set of all possible items that can be recommended. Let u be a utility function that measures the usefulness of item s to the user c . Then, for each user c , we want to choose items s' , that

maximize the utility function. After that, we will recommend those with higher values in this function. In many times, the proposed solutions process the sets C and S and return the recommendation list, without the explicit calculus of the utility values. The method proposed in this paper can be classified as one of these approaches.

The main classification of recommenders (Adomavicius & Tuzhilin, 2005) is based on their way to produce final suggestions. This is contained in three categories:

- Content-based (Pazzani & Billsus, 2007): Those that take into account the features of the user preferences to establish a recommendation model.
- Collaborative filtering (Ben Schafer, Frankowski, Herlocker & Sen, 2007): Those that use the preferences of similar users to produce suggestions. They could be classified in memory-based methods when they directly use preferences values to generate recommendations, or model-based if initially build an intermediate model to enclose known preferences.
- Hybrids (Burke, 2007): Those that combine concepts of both previous categories to generate recommendations.

E-commerce and e-learning are the most important application fields for recommendation systems. Specifically, e-learning recommender systems (Rafaeli, Dan-Gur & Barak, 2005) have been an active research field in the last years. Zaïane (2002) defines a recommender system in an e-learning context, as a software agent that tries to “intelligently” recommend actions to a learner based on the actions of previous learners, and proposes the use of association rule mining to discover associations between actions, sequences of actions and URLs, using them to suggest unknown items. In (Zhu, Ip, Fok & Cao, 2007), the authors use collaborative filtering to make recommendations for a learner about what should be learned before taking the next step in the learning process, and in (Khribi, Jemni & Nasraoui, 2008), the same recommendation approach is used to recommend links to the active user. In (García, Romero, Ventura & De Castro, 2009), the authors build a system to find, share and suggest to professors the most appropriate modifications to improve online courses effectiveness, using rule mining on the use of available information by students. Finally, the work already referred in (De la Fuente et. al, 2013) specifically focuses on programming task suggestions, but depends on additional information like precedence between problems, and is conceived for relatively few tasks.

Romero and Ventura (2010) show that most of e-learning recommender systems are built for specific domains. The majority of the referred systems, which can be classified as hybrids, have an important content dependence. Many of them are embedded into LMSs, and another group is built over learning object repositories, requiring the use of information behind metadata.

The work proposed at (Zaïane, 2002) is an important exception related with this criterion, because it proposes to use association rules between generic items to generate recommendations. Usually, association rule mining has been used to build recommendation methods applied to

different scenarios (Amatriain, Jaimes, Oliver & Pujol, 2011). As examples, Mobasher, Dai, Luo and Nakagawa (2001) present a system for web personalization based on association rule mining, identifying association rules from pageviews co-occurrences based on user navigational patterns. Lin, Alvarez and Ruiz (2002) present a new association rule mining algorithm that adjust the minimum support of the rules, in order to obtain a significant number of rules for each user and item. Cho, Kim and Kim (2002) combine decision trees and association rule mining in a web shop recommender system, and use association rules to link related items. Finally, Kazienko (2009) uses indirect association rules to discover not direct associations existing between web pages that rarely occur together but there are other, third “pages”, called transitive, with which they appear relatively frequent.

Respect to the usual content dependence in e-learning recommender systems, in the current problem we just have information on submission history and minimal information about problems, so we lack of additional information of individual users. For this reason, we are not able to adapt most of the previous works to our problem. Then, we have to create our proposal using a more general point of view in the research field. In addition, we will compare our final proposal against a baseline that combines the works at (Zañane, 2002) and (Lin et. al., 2002) to generate recommendations using association rules.

A RECOMMENDATION APPROACH FOR THE ONLINE JUDGE

The necessary information to generate recommendations is basically contained in the online judge database. Specifically, we have a set of submissions, each one conformed by a 3-tuple <user, problem, verdict> that represent an intent to solve the corresponding problem by the corresponding user, giving the corresponding verdict (accepted, wrong answer, time limit exceeded, runtime error, or compile error). Primarily, we do not have additional information on users and problems.

Considering this lack of information, and also the nature of the online judges, that contain a great community with smaller groups of people that share the same specific interest, we opt for a collaborative filtering approach over the content-based one. Works like (Zhu et.al, 2007)(Khribi et al, 2008) report positive results using this approach in e-learning scenarios.

In this case, we transform our data into a format that can support collaborative filtering recommendations (Ben Schafer et. al, 2007). The transformation is composed by a boolean vector for each user, where each element corresponds with a given problem. Each position receives a value of 1 if the user has the corresponding problem solved, and 0 otherwise. Table 1 shows, as an example, a hypothetical user-problem matrix. In this case, user *lagiro* has *Problem_1*, *Problem_3* and *Problem_4* as accepted problems, and user *yclmente* has solved *Problem_3* and *Problem_4*.

Table 1. Users vs problems matrix

		<i>problems</i>			
		Problem_1	Problem_2	Problem_3	Problem_4
<i>users</i>	lagiro	1	0	1	1
	yclemente	0	0	1	1
	rwrobinson	1	1	0	0
	lgvallejo	1	0	0	1

Memory-based collaborative filtering can be easily adapted to make recommendations in this scenario, where the goal is to provide a list of problems to solve. Considering the mentioned user's target in programming online judge, the application of a user-user approach can be interpreted as "recommend to the active user, those problems solved by the rest of the users that have a similar behavior with the active one, considering problems solved and not solved". With this purpose, we initially obtain a neighborhood of users for the active one, using a specific similarity measure. Then, we score each problem not solved by the active user, considering neighbors that have solved them; and finally we suggest those with larger scores.

Pearson's correlation coefficient is usually used as similarity measure in collaborative filtering when ratings provided by users are continuous data. However, in this scenario the user-problem matrix just contains categories (solved or not solved), and for this reason Pearson's application is not suitable. In these cases, alternative measures like Simple Matching coefficient and Jaccard coefficient have been employed (Amatriain et. al., 2011). Jaccard coefficient measures the overlap between two sets A and B, and is defined as $|A \cap B| / |A \cup B|$ (Manning, 2008). In this work, we follow this idea to define a similarity function between two users in the recommender system dataset (Table 2). This function initially receives the complete profile for the users (rows in table 1), and to perform comparison between them, it excludes from the analysis those problems tagged as zero (0) for both users. Then, for the remaining problems, it calculates the amount that contains the same category in both users, and finally returns as the similarity value, the ratio between this quantity and the amount of remaining problems.

Table 2. Similarity function between two users for collaborative filtering online judge scenario

Procedure Similarity(rowUser1, rowUser2)

1. num=0, den=0
 2. n=size(rowUser1)
 3. **for** i = 1 to n
 4. **if**(rowUser1[i] != 0 or rowUser2[i] != 0)
 5. den++
 6. **if**(rowUser1[i] == rowUser2[i])
 7. num++
 8. **end for**
 9. **return** num/den
-

A comparison of two users using this function would be as follows. Taking as an example to rwrobinson and lgvallejo in table 1, at least one of them have solved three problems (Problem_1,

Problem_2 and Problem_4), but they have the same result just for Problem_1, so their similarity value is $1/3$, that is 0.33.

Table 3 presents the method to suggest problems to solve using this similarity function. It receives the active user to give recommendations, the binary user-problem matrix, and the quantity of desired recommendations. In the first stage (lines 1-5), we calculate the similarities between the active user and the rest of users, store them in a local matrix w , and downwardly sort users according to the similarity values. Then, we get the top K similar users (line 6), and we score each problem not solved by the active one as the amount of neighbors that solved it (lines 7-11). Finally, we return the top n problems with higher scores.

Table 3. User-user collaborative filtering adapted to online judge scenario

Procedure CF(activeUser, matrixUserProb, n)

1. **for each** user u different from activeUser
 2. $w[u, \text{activeUser}] = \text{Similarity}(u, \text{activeUser})$
 3. $\text{neighbors.add}(u)$
 4. **end for**
 5. **sort** neighbors downwardly, according to $w[u, \text{activeUser}]$ values
 6. $\text{topKNeighbors} = \text{neighbors.subList}(0, K)$
 7. $\text{scores}[] = \{0\}$
 8. **for each** user u in topKNeighbors
 9. **for each** problem p
 10. **if**($\text{matrixUserProb}[u,p] == 1$ and $\text{matrixUserProb}[\text{activeUser},p] != 1$)
 11. $\text{scores}[p]++$
 12. **end for**
 13. **end for**
 14. **return** list of n problems with larger score values
-

This framework does not incorporate specific online judge data in the recommendation process. Like general-purpose collaborative filtering, in this case it just considers that a user u successfully solves a problem p ($\text{matrix}[u, p]=1$), or it do not solve it ($\text{matrix}[u, p]=0$). To incorporate information on user's failure in the recommendation process, we propose to modify the binary user-problem matrix to reflect this domain-specific data and add granularity to the user profiles. In the following sections we present three possible modifications to perform in this direction. For all cases, the function in table 2 will be used to determine the similarity between users.

User's fails in a problem, as a new category (UserFails)

The first modification proposed to the original matrix (table 1) focus on separate as a new category those problems that the users try to solve but fail it, receiving at least some failure category previously mentioned. We assign a new discrete category ($\text{matrix}[u, p]=2$) in these cases, in addition to "success in a problem" ($\text{matrix}[u, p]=1$), and to "no knowledge about a problem", that is the new meaning in this case for ($\text{matrix}[u, p]=0$).

For each user-problem intersection with the value 0 in the original matrix, we calculate the amount of failures (belonging to any category) for the current user trying to solve the current problem. If this amount exceeds the value of zero (0), then we replace the value 0 in the original matrix, with a new value 2.

After this transformation, the algorithm in table 3 could be used to generate the list of problems to solve. For each user, it allows the recommendation of unknown problems (value 0), and problems previously failed by him/her (value 2).

User's fails in a problem, as two different categories (UserFails2)

A second alternative to modify the user-problem matrix assumes the separation of failed problems in two categories: those where the amount of failures is under a predefined threshold th , and those where the amount is equal or over this threshold. This approach also increases the granularity in the user profiles.

For each user-problem intersection tagged with the value 2 (using previous method), we remain this value ($matrix[u, p]=2$) if the number of failures is under the threshold th . Otherwise, if this number is equal or over th , then we set ($matrix[u, p]=3$).

Algorithm in table 3 could also be used to generate recommendations in this scenario, because the solved problems are completely covered by the value 1.

User's fails and user's delay in a problem, each one as two different categories (UserFD)

In order to incorporate more specific information from the online judge to improve the accuracy in the recommendations, we propose a third method that also considers two categories in the accepted exercises. It assumes that users usually get difficulty to solve some exercises, and need to do many failures before the final acceptance. In contrast, other exercises can be solved usually with few submissions. In this approach, we treat these scenarios as two different categories.

In this case, the user-problem intersection could be tagged with five different values, using two thresholds $th1$ and $th2$, as follows.

- $matrix[u,p]=0$, if the user u never tries to solve the problem p
- $matrix[u,p]=1$, if the user u solved the problem p , needing less than $th1$ failures before
- $matrix[u,p]=2$, if the user u solved the problem p , needing $th1$ or more than $th1$ failures before
- $matrix[u,p]=3$, if the user u not solved the problem p , and its number of failures is under $th2$
- $matrix[u,p]=4$, if the user u not solved the problem p , and its number of failures is equal or over $th2$

In this modification, the categories 1 and 2 cover solved problems. For this reason, we need to modify the algorithm in table 3, to get recommendations with this transformation. This modification just implies the replacement of line 10, with the line in table 4, to consider in this case all the accepted problems in the recommendation generation.

Table 4. New condition for the “user’s fails and user’s delay in a problem” method

<code>if((matrixUserProb[u,p]== 1 or matrixUserProb[u,p]== 2) and (matrixUserProb[activeUser,p]!= 1 and matrixUserProb[activeUser,p]!= 2))</code>

EXPERIMENTATION AND RESULTS

In this work, we performed offline experiments using a dataset obtained from an international programming online judge: the Caribbean Online Judge (<http://coj.uci.cu>). This online judge was initially deployed in 2010, and currently it has attracted lots of users from more than 20 countries. Considering the historical submissions, we build a synthetic dataset, with 1910 users and 575 problems where users have solved, as average, around 42 problems. These data are specifically represented as a set of the previously explained 3-tuples with the form (user, problem, verdict); and it exactly contains 151667 3-tuples. This format allows to easily build a user-problem matrix (table 1), and to perform the modifications proposed in UserFails, UserFails2, and UserFD. To our best knowledge, this work is among the pioneers on the use of a synthetic dataset extracted for a real e-learning recommendation systems scenario.

The experimental framework was prepared following Gunawardana and Shani suggestions (Gunawardana & Shani, 2009) for offline recommender systems evaluation. They proposed to divide the dataset in training and test set, use the training set and the algorithm to evaluate to generate recommendations, and finally compare these recommendations against the test set. In this case, to build the training set, for each user we sample a set of problems solved; and then the problems not selected but solved are used to create the test set. We repeat this procedure several times, and for each one, a different training-test pair was obtained and stored. Our approach also takes as input the failures for each user-problem, and for this reason they are also stored independently. Considering that our training and test set just contains 3-tuples associated with problems solved, each training and test set contains around 30000 entries, which represents a part of the total number of 3-tuples associated to the different verdicts.

Precision and recall are metrics usually used to measure accuracy in the “recommending good items” task (Gunawardana & Shani, 2009), and consequently, we apply them in this scenario to evaluate our method. Considering the classification of the possible result of recommending an item to a user (table 5), precision is defined as the ratio of items recommended and preferred, over the total of recommended items. On the other hand, recall is defined as the ratio of items recommended and preferred, over the total of preferred items (table 6).

Table 5. Possible recommendation result considering actually preferred items.

	<i>Recommended</i>	<i>Not recommended</i>
Preferred	True-Positive (tp)	False-Negative (fn)
Not preferred	False-Positive (fp)	True-Negative (tn)

Table 6. Definitions for precision and recall

$precision = \frac{\#tp}{\#tp + \#fp}$	$recall = \frac{\#tp}{\#tp + \#fn}$
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In our experiment, for each user, the items to be recommended are obtained using the training set, the corresponding algorithm, and failures data. Using the items to be recommended and the list of problems in the test set (representing preferred items), the precision and recall values can be easily calculated. For each user, we will compute its current precision and recall and then, we obtain the final accuracy as the average precision and recall using all users. This procedure is done for each training-test pair, and finally we average all precision and recall values to obtain the precision and recall results for the current trial. For the experiments, we will assume a value $K=80$ (in table 3, line 5) for the amount of nearest neighbors.

Experiments were conducted to complete three different goals: 1) to adjust the best values for the parameters th , $th1$ and $th2$, 2) to measure the influence of the proposal for improving the recommendation accuracy, and 3) to compare it against a state-of-art method for e-learning scenarios.

We perform several trials for the approaches in UserFails2 and UserFD to obtain the best values for the parameters th , $th1$ and $th2$. Table 7 presents precision and recall values for UserFails2, modifying the th values in the range [2; 11]. Both optimal values were obtained for $th=2$, and then this value is taken for the further evaluations. Values for $th1$ and $th2$ were also obtained using empirical evaluations, varying $th1$ in the range {1, 3, 5} and $th2$ in {1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15}. Table 8 and 9 present the results, where the best values were obtained for $th1=5$ and $th2=5$. For all trials, we assume $n=5$ for the amount of desired recommendations (Table 3).

Table 7. Precision and Recall for different th values in the UserFails2 method

<i>th</i>	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Precision	0,7763	0,7756	0,7733	0,7750	0,7720	0,7697	0,7680	0,7651	0,7644	0,7654
Recall	0,1639	0,1624	0,1623	0,1629	0,1623	0,1617	0,1615	0,1613	0,1602	0,1606

Table 8. Precision for different $th1$ and $th2$ values in the UserFD method.

<i>th1\th2</i>	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15
1	0,7641	0,7677	0,7726	0,7671	0,7644	0,7654	0,7648	0,7641
3	0,7631	0,7759	0,7687	0,7644	0,7690	0,7651	0,7657	0,7644
5	0,7664	0,7763	0,7769	0,7713	0,7671	0,7661	0,7667	0,7638

Table 9. Recall for different th1 and th2 values in the UserFD method.

<i>th1\th2</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>15</i>
1	0,1599	0,1614	0,1623	0,1609	0,1604	0,1603	0,1602	0,1593
3	0,1600	0,1634	0,1616	0,1603	0,1615	0,1606	0,1602	0,1602
5	0,1611	0,1634	0,1645	0,1624	0,1618	0,1610	0,1610	0,1607

These values (for th, th1 and th2) were used to compare the three proposals against our baseline (the method using just the matrix with ones and zeros). For each method, we vary the size of the recommendations list in the range [5, 40], presenting the corresponding precision and recall values in tables 10 and 11.

Table 10. Precision values for the presented approaches, modifying the size of recommendation list.

<i>n</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>25</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>35</i>	<i>40</i>
CF_baseline	0,7687	0,6924	0,6289	0,5777	0,5351	0,5003	0,4688	0,4422
CF_UserFails	0,7687	0,6990	0,6361	0,5875	0,5471	0,5115	0,4794	0,4539
CF_UserFails2	0,7763	0,7037	0,6402	0,5916	0,5493	0,5116	0,4800	0,4530
CF_UserFD	0,7769	0,7032	0,6400	0,5882	0,5463	0,5109	0,4810	0,4537

Table 11. Recall values for the presented approaches, modifying the size of recommendation list.

<i>n</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>25</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>35</i>	<i>40</i>
CF_baseline	0,1614	0,2744	0,3549	0,4184	0,4679	0,5103	0,5431	0,5722
CF_UserFails	0,1615	0,2786	0,3625	0,4286	0,4835	0,5244	0,5588	0,5912
CF_UserFails2	0,1639	0,2809	0,3654	0,4323	0,4859	0,5261	0,5600	0,5906
CF_UserFD	0,1645	0,2821	0,3653	0,4295	0,4812	0,5239	0,5611	0,5914

They show that the precision and recall are improved when the information about fails and delays by user is incorporated in the recommendation process. Best precision and recall values were obtained by CF_UserFD for the lowest value of n, and by CF_UserFails2 for the majority of higher values. Results also show that the information about previous failures to solve a problem (CF_UserFD), usually decreases the recommendation accuracy for larger n, comparing with approaches that just consider failures over finally unsolved problems (CF_UserFails and CF_UserFails2).

Also, we can interpret and justify the optimal values obtained for the parameters th, th1 and th2, associated to the methods CF_UserFails2 and CF_UserFD, and presented in tables 7, 8 and 9. At the first case, the optimal performance for CF_UserFails2 was for th=2. It means that the best separation of failed problems in two categories, is assuming that the problems with at most one failure belong to the first category, and the others to the second one. We can associate this result with the fact that there are two possible attitudes associated to a user dealing with troubles in a problem solution: 1) it tries to solved the problem just a time, and if it fails, it does not try again because thinks that it is not following the correct way (the first category), and 2) it continuously

tries to solve the problem several times following different alternatives and possible ways (the second category).

As second, we can justify the optimal values for th_1 and th_2 in CF_UserFD using a similar reasoning. In this case the optimal behavior was achieved for $th_1=5$ and $th_2=5$, but we must note that for th_2 , that has the same meaning that th in $CF_UserFails2$, we obtain a similar behavior for $th_2=3$. Like $CF_UserFails2$, in this case the best performance was obtained for lower values in the threshold associated to user's fails in a problem, and then this behavior receives the same explanation associated to the previous method. We remark the fact that $th_2=5$ represents a small value for the threshold, because the tables show that longer values like $th_2=15$ still imply modifications on the accuracy of the method. On the other hand, related to th_1 , we initially assumed in CF_UserFD that a similar threshold to the user's fails, but associated to the user's delays in finally solved problems, would imply a notably improvement on the recommendation accuracy. However, for $th_1>5$, the precision and recall values associated to CF_UserFD tends to the values in $CF_UserFails2$ (this information was not shown in the tables). In addition, the method performs worse than $CF_UserFails2$ for $th_1=1$ and $th_1=3$, and then just slightly improves it for $th_1=5$. We believe that this behavior means that, for the recommendation purposes, there are no differences between users that solve a problem at the first submission, and those that need at most four submissions to solve it. However, the improvement also show that for some cases (users with more than four fails), CF_UserFD could effectively outperform the previous methods.

Tables 10 and 11 present the precision and recall values for different values of n . As was expected, when n increases, the precision value decreases and the recall value increases. Then, the optimal value to assign to n is still an open question. We believe that this value strongly depends on the final users and the system design associated to this method. However, in this work we will give another criterion that could be useful to choose n . With this purpose, we use the metric F1 (Herlocker, Konstan, Terveen, & Riedl, 2004), as a way to combine the precision and recall values (table 12). Then, we present in table 13 the values of F1 that were calculated using data in tables 10 and 11. Following them, the best balance between precision and recall was obtained for the method $CF_UserFails2$ and $n=30$. However, for $n\geq 20$ the values of F1 tends to be approximately constant, and then, considering that a long recommendation list could affect the final user selection, we suggest $n=20$ as a good value for the size of the recommendation list. On the other hand, although we have showed the goodness of $CF_UserFails2$, our final suggestion to incorporate the proposal in a real system, is to alternate between $CF_UserFails2$ and CF_UserFD , because we have presented reasons that justify that the second one could perform better in some scenarios.

Table 12. Definition for the metric F1

$$F1 = \frac{2 * precision * recall}{precision + recall}$$

Table 13. F1 values for the presented approaches, modifying the size of recommendation list.

<i>n</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>25</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>35</i>	<i>40</i>
CF_baseline	0,2667	0,3930	0,4537	0,4853	0,4992	0,5052	0,5032	0,4988
CF_UserFails	0,2669	0,3984	0,4618	0,4956	0,5133	0,5178	0,5160	0,5135
CF_UserFails2	0,2706	0,4015	0,4652	0,4995	0,5156	0,5187	0,5169	0,5127
CF_UserFD	0,2715	0,4026	0,4651	0,4964	0,5116	0,5173	0,5179	0,5134

Finally, we compare our results against the association rule mining approach to e-learning recommender systems proposed by Zaïane, and previously referred (Zaïane, 2002). Rules were obtained using the method proposed by (Lin et. al, 2002), where they mine rules (for recommendation) with just one item in the consequent, taking in this scenario the form $\langle \text{problem1, solved} \rangle$ and $\langle \text{problem2, solved} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{problem3, solved} \rangle$. Like (Lin et. al, 2002), these rules were mined, for each problem, with an apriori-like method verifying a minimal confidence and an adaptive support, obtaining a set that verifies that its length lies in a desired interval. To generate recommendations, also similar to (Lin et.al, 2002), for each user we score each unsolved problem following two steps: 1) we select the rules (for the current problem) whose antecedent matches the current user, and 2) we score the problem as the sum of the product of the confidence and the support of the selected rules. Finally we present the items with the higher scores in the recommendation list to the user.

We performed several trials to adjust the parameters in this method (possible interval for the size of the rule set for each problem, and minimal confidence). Best values were obtained for the interval [10; 50], and for a confidence value $\text{minConf}=0,3$, assuming $n=5$ for the top n recommendations. Then, we compare this approach (Rule-Based) against CF_UserFails2, which performs best considering our proposals, and also against the baseline (CF_baseline). Tables 12 and 13 present the results in terms of precision and recall, varying n in the range [5; 30]. We excluded $n=35$ and $n=40$ because as we previously showed, its use is actually impractical in real scenarios. For all cases, the precision and recall values for Rule-Based are notably under CF_UserFails2, and even under CF_baseline.

In this case we also perform a statistical comparison considering CF_UserFails2 against Rule-Based using Wilcoxon test considering precision and recall values for each independent user (Gunawardana & Shani, 2009), in order to determine if the difference between the methods is significant. For all n , CF_UserFails2 also statistically outperforms Rule-Based with $p<0,000$.

Table 14. Comparing rule-based method against presented approaches. Precision values.

<i>n</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>25</i>	<i>30</i>
CF_baseline	0,7687	0,6924	0,6289	0,5777	0,5351	0,5003
CF_UserFails2	0,7763	0,7037	0,6402	0,5916	0,5493	0,5116
Rule-Based	0,7618	0,6751	0,6158	0,5673	0,5311	0,5011

Table 15. Comparing rule-based method against presented approaches. Recall values.

<i>N</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>25</i>	<i>30</i>
CF_baseline	0,1614	0,2744	0,3549	0,4184	0,4679	0,5103
CF_UserFails2	0,1639	0,2809	0,3654	0,4323	0,4859	0,5261
Rule-Based	0,1601	0,2650	0,3441	0,4027	0,4537	0,4957

In addition, CF_UserFails2 notably improves Rule-Based in terms of execution time. We performed an experiment over a framework composed by a Windows XP Professional Operating System, a Pentium ® Dual Core 3.06 GHz Microprocessor, and a 4 Gb RAM Memory, and in this scenario, our method (using different values in th , and the values employed in the previous trials for the rest of the general parameters) takes around 109 milliseconds to generate a list of recommendations for a single user. On the other hand, Rule-Based (using the same parameter values associated to the previous trial) initially needs around 4 minutes to obtain the rules used to generate the recommendations. Similarly to our method, using these rules the final list was obtained in few milliseconds.

Summarizing, results show that there are more than two different kinds of interaction between users and problems in a programming online judge. For each user, in addition to consider the group of problems solved and the rest of problems, there is an important third group composed by those problems that the user tries to solved but failed, because taking it into account, the recommendation is considerably improved. Finally, the approach presented in this work also outperforms a state-of-art association rules-based method proposed to generate recommendations in an e-learning scenario.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

In this paper we present programming online judges as particular e-learning scenarios where the inclusion of recommendation functionalities could overcome the information overload associated to the number of users and problems. We show that the majority of previous works in e-learning recommender systems are highly domain-dependant, so it cannot be applied to recommend programming problems to be solved, in the mentioned scenario.

To create a recommender framework for these applications, we adopt a basic collaborative filtering approach that initially considers just problems solved or not solved. We also propose several ways to incorporate specific judge's information in the recommendation process, like problems that the students try to solve but they fail, and problems where students usually needs several failed intents before accept them.

We perform offline experiments using data from a real-time online judge. Results show that the incorporation of specific online judge information to the recommendation process notably improves the accuracy in precision and recall terms, comparing with the general-purpose

baseline, and also over a recommendation approach using association rules and proposed for e-learning scenarios.

This framework could be incorporated to any online judge platform, to guide students to select the right problem to be solved. We think that it implicitly contains pedagogical values and also helps competitive students to have many problems solved, because it is based on personal user profiles.

Currently, we are developing new ideas to continue and improve our work. We focus on ideas that could improve recommendation just using available data, so we will not propose to incorporate additional information to users or problems, like categories, demographic data, and others. We think that the most important extensions could be:

- Our method just considers success or failure on problem solutions, but do not explore the standard failure categories (wrong answer, runtime error, time limit exceeded). To process this information will allow us to extract new knowledge that could also be useful in the recommendation generation.
- The online judge also has timespans for each user-problem interaction. The convenient use of timespans could improve the recommendation performance.
- Redefine the “recommendation quality” concept. We measure the method accuracy using the traditional precision and recall metrics, but this one partially regards the impact of the recommendations in the final users. This is a major issue, and to evaluate it, maybe online experiments will be needed.

REFERENCES

- Adomavicius, G., Tuzhilin, A. (2005). Toward the next generation of recommender systems: a survey of state-of-the-art and possible extensions. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, 17(6), 734-749
- Amatriain, X., Jaimes, A., Oliver, N., & Pujol, J. M. (2011). Data mining methods for recommender systems. In Ricci, F., Rokach, L., Shapira, B., Kantor, P.B. (eds.), *Recommender Systems Handbook* (pp. 39-72). Springer, Heidelberg.
- Ben Schafer, J., Frankowski, D., Herlocker, J., & Sen, S. (2007). Collaborative Filtering Recommender Systems. In: Brusilovsky, P., Kobsa, A., Nejdl, W. (eds.), *The adaptive web: Methods and Strategies of Web Personalization*. LNCS, vol. 4321 (pp. 291-324). Springer, Heidelberg.
- Burke, R. (2007). Hybrid Web Recommender Systems. In: Brusilovsky, P., Kobsa, A., Nejdl, W. (eds.), *The adaptive web: Methods and Strategies of Web Personalization*. LNCS, vol. 4321 (pp. 377-408). Springer, Heidelberg.
- Cheang, B., Kurnia, A., Lim, A., Wee, Ch. O.(2003). On automated grading of programming assignments in an academic institution. *Computers & Education*, 41(2), 121-131.

- Cho, Y., Kim, J., Kim, S. (2002). A personalized recommender system based on web usage mining and decision tree induction. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 23, 329-342.
- De la Fuente, L., Pardo, A., Delgado Kloos, C. (2013). Addressing drop-out and sustained effort issues with large practical groups using an automated delivery and assessment system. *Computers & Education*, 61, 33-42.
- García, E., Romero, C., Ventura, S., & De Castro, C. (2009). An architecture for making recommendations to courseware authors using association rule mining and collaborative filtering. *User Modeling and User-Adapted Interaction*, 19, 99-132.
- Gunawardana, A., & Shani, G. (2009). A survey of accuracy evaluation metrics of recommendation tasks. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 10, 2935-2962.
- Herlocker, J. L., Konstan, J. A., Terveen, L. G., & Riedl, J. T. (2004). Evaluating collaborative filtering recommender systems. *ACM Transactions on Information Systems (TOIS)*, 22(1), 5-53.
- Kazienko, P. (2009). Mining indirect association rules for web recommendation. *International Journal of Applied Mathematics and Computer Science*, 19, 165-186.
- Khribi, M. K., Jemni, M., & Nasraoui, O. (2008). Automatic Recommendations for E-Learning Personalization Based on Web Usage Mining Techniques and Information Retrieval. In *Proceeding of IEEE International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies* (pp. 241-245). IEEE Computer Society.
- Kosowski, A., Malafiejski, M., Noinski, T. (2007). Application of an online judge & contester system in academic tuition. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Web-based Learning*, LNCS, vol. 4823 (pp. 343-354). Springer, Heidelberg.
- Kurnia, A., Lim, A., Cheang, B. (2001). Online judge. *Computers & Education*, 36(4), 299-315.
- Lin, W., Alvarez, S., & Ruiz, C. (2002). Efficient adaptive-support association rule mining for recommender systems, *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, 6, 83-105.
- Manning, C. (2008). *An introduction to information retrieval*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Mobasher, B., Dai, H., Luo, T., Nakagawa, M. (2001). Effective personalization based on association rule discovery from web usage data. In *Proceedings of the 3rd International Workshop On Web Information and Data Management (WIDM)* (pp. 9-15). ACM Press.
- Pazzani, M., & Billsus, D. (2007). Content-based Recommendation Systems. In: Brusilovsky, P., Kobsa, A., Nejdl, W. (eds.): *The adaptive web: Methods and Strategies of Web Personalization*. LNCS, vol. 4321 (pp. 325-341). Springer, Heidelberg.
- Rafaeli, S., Dan-Gur, Y., & Barak, M. (2005). Social recommender system: recommendations in support of e-learning. *International Journal of Distance Education Technologies (IJDET)*, 3(2), 30-47.
- Resnick, P., & Varian, R. (1997). Recommender systems. *Communications of the ACM*, 40, 56-58.
- Romero, C., & Ventura, S. (2010). Educational data mining: a review of the state of the art. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man and Cybernetics – Part C Applications and Reviews*, 40, 601-618.
- Skiena, S., & Revilla, M. (2003). *Programming challenges*. New York: Springer-Verlag.

- Zaïane, O. (2002). Building a recommender agent for e-learning systems. In *Proceedings of the International Conference in Education* (pp. 55-59). IEEE Computer Society.
- Zhu, F., Ip, H., Fok, A., & Cao, J. (2007). PeRES: A personalized recommendation education system based on multi-agents & SCORM. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Web-based Learning*, LNCS, vol. 4823 (pp. 31-42). Springer, Heidelberg.